

ABOUT THE THEME OF HISTORICAL LEGENDS IN KARAKALPAK FOLKLORE

Elmuratov R.Kh

Karakalpak State University named after Berdak

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Annotation: Legends, which include part of the folklore heritage, are one of the main genres of oral creativity of the Turkic peoples. In the world science of folklore and literary criticism, a large number of works have been published on the definition of theoretical descriptions of legends. As you know, one of the main genres of folk art is that historical events are preserved to a certain extent in legends, which creates some opportunities for us to understand and learn about our past history, our primordial national culture, our literature. It is known that in modern world folklore a structural-semantic concept is developing, which is aimed at identifying and classifying the specifics, genre features of folklore-epic genres, i.e. fairy tales, myths, legends, etc. features from all sides, is the basis for the classification of folklore genres, plot and motives. Therefore, in this article we have tried to describe the legends, one of the epic genres of folklore, and their idea-themes and content. The problems of dividing historical legends into thematic types in Karakalpak folklore are also determined.

Key words: meaning, folklore, historical legend, historical figure, image, genre, hero, plot, motive, episode, typology.

Widespread use of typological and artistic analysis methods in world folklore studies, deepening of the volume of studies aimed at determining the essence of each literary tradition, creates a wide opportunity for learning the folklore. Therefore, it is a proven fact that this scientific concept of the interrelationship of artistic-aesthetic aspects and their development in connection with historical-heritage is related to the determination of the reasons for the realization of the national transformation of epic genres in the folklore of genetically related peoples. From this point of view, one of the epic genres in the folklore of the Turkic peoples originates from the characteristics, ideas and themes of the legends and different national versions of them appeared in the folklore of each people. When we compare them, we can see similarities and differences in the plot, motives and themes of the legends. In this article, we will talk about the themes of historical legends and their typology in Karakalpak folklore.

As we all know, "Aniz" is an Arabic word that means poetry, prose, fiction. That is, to tell something from someone's language. It is a genre of folkloric folklore that depicts stories and legends passed down from generation

to generation, sometimes with the help of textiles, sometimes with the help of textiles. The volume is short - consists of two or three episodes, does not have a traditional style form. Generally it begins with narration of a simple story and is freely understood in the process of passing from mouth to mouth. In the legend, there are hadiths related to events and historical figures. The story is based on the historical truth and is not restricted from the thematic side. In legends we can see mostly past experiences, moral virtues, vices in human character, events related to the marriage and business of famous people are discussed, and the lack of ideal dimensions of morality is evaluated. Such characteristics are known by each legend as their own instructions and etiquette.

In legends, we can mostly see historical figures, kings, prophets, holy saints and others real images and they have also their own artistic interpretation. One of the most exaggerated images in the historical narratives of the world and Turkish folklore is the image of historical figures. In the plot of the legend, historical figures appear as protagonists or episodic characters and perform their own artistic function. In historical legends, the image of a historical figure is portrayed as a brave, manly, business-like, wise person who protects the people, and by highlighting the humane qualities of the historical figure and artistically portraying his actions for the people, the historical figure rises to the level of an ideal hero. Therefore, people manage to create prototype images of historical figures. As it is known from folklore data, legends involving historical figures are divided into several types:

1. prophets and holy saints, legends depicting the images of prophets ("Hazreti Ali's regret", "Hazreti Ali's anger", "Hazreti Ali's kindness", "Suleyman's kindness to the bat", "Prophet Suleyman's test", "Prophet and Magpie" and etc;

2. legends with the image of rules or military commanders, warriors ("Muraly-Sher and Sultan Suyin's story", "Maman Biy's Dream", "Maman Biy's descent in Title", "Esengeldi and Aydos biy", "Aydos biy", "Ernazar Alakoz - Noker", "Ispandiyar Khan", "Arastu's will to Alexander" and others;

3. legends with the image of famous Healers ("Marrying Hakim Ulykpan's son", "About Aplatun's piety and Alastun's ingenuity" and others;

4. some historical legends related to genealogy, clans, communities and their origin are connected with a historical person or a person who has made history in history, legends that illustrate the image of historical figures are "Kipchaks" and others.

5. legends with the image of a poet and a baqsi: Alisher Navayi, Babur, Makhtymkuly, Ajiniyaz, Berdakh and others can be an example.

6. place names and legends about cities ("Nur ata", "Nazlymkhan Suliv", "Khalkabad", etc.)

As it is known from the data, it has its own tradition of glorifying the image of prophets and holy saints in oral and written works. In the works of art, the views of the people about the educated person are described based on the image of the prophets. Therefore, there are several legends about prophets, holy saints among the people and in folklore. In these legends, events related to the deeds of prophets and holy saints and holy things that they consider to be sacred are narrated. It should also be mentioned that the image of prophets and holy saints and saints is different from ordinary people. That is why, in legends, the mythical characteristics of these images are described more often.

The legend about Hazrat Aliy can be an example for the legend with the image of a historical person - a saint. The legends about Hazrat Ali were very widespread in Eastern countries, and they were collected by folklorists among the people and prepared for publication. For example, we can find it in 100 volumes of Karakalpak folklore, "Hazreti Ali", "Hazreti Ali's regret", "Hazret Ali's anger", "Hazret Ali's goodness" and others.

Hazrat Ali is one of the assistants of the Prophet Muhammad, the fourth of the Sharyars. Muhammad's son-in-law. He was born in 600. Ali ibn Abu Talib ruled from 656 to 661, i.e. 4 years and 7 months. Ali is considered the first imam of the Shia in Islam. He is considered a historical person. That's why in the legends about Hazrat Ali, it is possible to see how he helped and supported people who were in trouble.

According to the legend of Hazrat Ali, Hazrat Ali is the prophet's son-in-law. He is the leader of Shiites, we are Sunnis. It is not known whether Hazrat Ali came to this place or not. But the narrators says that " Hazrat Ali came to Nur". There is a place of Idyk camel in the mountain of Nur. It is called "the resting place of Hazrat Ali's camel". There is a similar trace on the stonestream at the top of the mountain. It looks like a tiger's track. It was only on the surface of the stone. Karakalpaks went to help Hazrat Ali. Hazrat Ali used to say "Kipchagym-koschagym" for the rest of his life.

Its legend is as follows:

Hazrat Ali could not take many people at the foot of Kap mountain. Now, when he was about to go back, he could see the dust in the distance. When he sends his man, he found out that it was Karakalpaks shouting the motto "White

knife!". When they arrived, Hazrat Ali said happily "Barekelle! Kup chaginda keldiniz, kup chaginda" The word "Kupchak" gradually became "Kypchak". In this way, this Kypchak subjugated the people of the mountain who did not convert to religion. This is when the Jabi took the motto "Dindi Jabi - Dashti Kypchak!" This is the story of Hazrat Ali.

In works spread among the people, events and hadiths are depicted with the help of this or that subject (the camel of Hazrat Ali, or Kap mountain) related to prophets, saints and the narrative style of a prophet, saint is performed.

About the contribution of this historical person to the treasure of world culture, as well as his services in the development of our holy religion, morals and manners, religious faith, universal human qualities, goodness and the artistic interpretation of the ideas that call for spiritual maturity occupy a special place in the folk works.

The moral virtues of Hazrat Ali are depicted in a high spirit, and the story describes him as a hero. The reason is that special attention is paid to his devotion to religion and the purity of his heart. It is shown that Hazrat Ali's honesty, purity of heart had an impact on evil, wicked people, and people who did not believe, calling them to religious faith and leading them to the path of righteousness.

According to one of the folk tales of this content, a poor man borrowed money from a rich man, and his debt increased to over a thousand gold. When the rich man came and asked the poor old man for a loan, the poor man said that he could not pay it yet. At that time, the poor old man had a teenage daughter. The rich man demands that the poor old man should give his daughter to settle the debt.

Begging the rich man to give him three days to pay back the debt, he came to Ali asking for help. Ali was fourteen years old at that time. Hearing the poor old man's problem, Ali said to Allahatala:

"Oh Lord, if you give me your blessing, I would save the daughter of this poor old man," he begged.

Hearing Ali's wish, Allah gave him his blessing. Then Ali set off with this poor old man. On the way, he said to Ali:

- My son, do you have cattle? Do you have a treasure? - he asked.

Then Ali:

"Grandpa, I don't have anything," he said.

- If you don't have any money, my son, how can you pay my debt? - he said.

Get on my back. Never open your eyes on the road! - he said to the old man. He took him to another village, dropped him on the ground, and said to him:

- Grandpa, this country has a slave market. Take me to this slave market and sell me for a thousand gold. I will arrange the next part myself, - he said.

When they both came to the slave market and asked the price of the slaves, there was no slave worth a thousand gold. Seeing this, Ali said:

"Tell everyone that I will do the work of a thousand slaves," he said.

A rich man who came to the slave market bought Ali for a thousand gold. The old man returned home and got rid of his debt. Ali started serving the rich man. There was a big wedding in the land of a rich man and he asked Ali to wrestle with a giant wrestler at this wedding. The giant wrestler tried to lift Ali and throw him. However, he could not move Ali. After that, he tried to hit Ali with a sword. At that time, by the power of God, Duldil horse and Zulfikar sword appeared near Ali. Ali's cut the giant wrestler in two with his sword. Fearing this, the infidel country converted to the Muslim religion.

Due to the narration of these stories, it is noted that the wisdom of Hazrat Ali, even though he put himself in difficulties, he helped the poor and the poor and won the victory with divine power, and was elevated to the rank of a saint.

There are several similar traditional motifs in the legends connected with the name of Hazrat Ali, in which the wisdom, broad-mindedness and divinity of Hazrat Ali attract our attention. It is known that the participation of a historical person in the genre of legend serves as one of the main factors in defining the specific characteristics and artistry of the models of epic writing.

Of course, the legends about our holy religion, holy saints which existed in the folklore of the people, the famous historical figures' faithfulness to their faith and Islam, their love and loyalty to Allah and listening to the opinions of Allah's will not make the listeners indifferent. The reason for this is that the artistic narratives of prophets, saints in legends have an effect on the heart of the listener to increase his love for Islam, which is his own religion, to create feelings of prayer and faith. Therefore, the legends created about religious historical figures are one of the artistic tools that inform the listener that if he understands God and loves him more, if they served in his path, they will be honored. Moreover, they are also very important in strengthening the love of God.

As it is known from the data, the images of the saints who we can see in the legends are divided into two types. The first of them is the image of Prophet-saints, and the second one is the image of caring saints. The image of Hazrat Aliy mentioned above belonged to the first type of images.

In Karakalpak folk legends, the image of a ruler, a military leader and a warrior is described in a particularly loving and noble spirit. For example, in Karakalpak folklore, Ernazar Alakoz is portrayed as a folk hero in the legend "Ernazar Alakoz - Noker".

In Karakalpak folklore, there are also legends in which the image of the well-known healers is depicted. For example, in Karakalpak folklore we have legends, "The wedding of Hakim Ulykpan's son", "About the wisdom of Aplatun and the ingenuity of Alastun" and others

A different type of historical legends related to genealogy, clans, communities and their origin are connected with a historical person or a person who has made history in history. Legends are also widespread in Karakalpak folklore. For example, in Karakalpak folklore, there is a legend called "Kipchaklar".

In Karakalpak folklore, there are also legends in which the image of a poet and a baqsi are depicted. For example, Jiyen Zhyraw, Ajiniyaz, Berdakh, etc. can be an example for such legends. Legends about poets and baqsi are also widespread, and they create their own special theme. Famous poets and baqsis' real life experiences, historical events, hadiths, and biographies are highlighted in them. Therefore, in this form of historical legends, the images of poets and baqsis are created.

In Karakalpak folklore, there are also legends about place names and cities that appeared in connection with historical persons and historical events. For example, in Karakalpak folklore, there is a legend called "Ayazkala":

"It is said that this city was named after a shepherd named Ayaz. "Bahyt kusy" landed on Ayaz's head and he becomes the Khan. He builds these cities. During his time as a khan, in order not to indulge in pride, he hung the clothes he wore when he was a shepherd:

"Ayaz Khan, don't forget who you were, always look at your shepherd's stick," he says, remembering the times when he was a shepherd

Here, as we have already seen, one of the traditional images, the image of the shepherd and the image of the king, are presented in parallel. This is what made the evolution of the image. That is, the first profession of the person named Ayaz in history was a shepherd, and then he became a king with the help

of the bird of fortune. Nevertheless, he is described as a mature person without losing his virtues.

In general, historical legends differ from other types of legends in their idea of theme and content. In legends related to historical persons, the historical person's personality qualities are described at a high level, the historical person is idealized and depicted as a holy person. If we compare this problem as an object of folklore, we can have the typology of it.

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